

THE POWER OF MIND CONTROL THROUGH HYPNOSIS

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ANNOTATION

The main essence of the article is the effect of hypnosis on the human mind, its influence, positive and negative features of hypnosis. For many years, information has been given about the areas in which hypnosis is used and the experiences that occur in a person in a hypnotic state. Researches and their results are also cited in the article.

Key words: hypnosis, consciousness, sleep, empiric, attention, hallucination, delusion, amnesia, posthypnotic amnesia, trance, superficial sleep.

Introduction Hypnosis is a special psychological state characterized by the functioning of a person at a level of consciousness with certain physiological properties, only superficially similar to sleep and different from the normal conscious state. This state is characterized by a high level of receptivity and sensitivity, which is usually given as much importance to internal empirical perceptions as it is to external reality. To some extent, we are all ready to be offered hypnosis. When people talk about standing with their eyes closed and moving backwards and forwards, most people are actually walking quite a bit. In fact, anyone who can focus and visualize can experience some degree of hypnosis. And almost everyone experiences hypnotic sensitivity.

The main part

A central phenomenon of hypnosis is suggestibility, the level of receptivity and sensitivity to suggestions and warnings provided by the hypnotist. Appropriate suggestions from a hypnotist can produce a wide range of psychological, emotional, and motor responses in deeply hypnotized individuals. By accepting and responding to prompts, the subject can pretend to be deaf, blind, paralyzed, hallucinating, delusional, amnesiac, impervious to pain, or uncomfortable bodily states. In addition, the subject may display various behavioral responses that the hypnotist sees as reasonable or desirable responses to the situation suggested by the hypnotist.

Results and discussion

Can hypnosis make people do things against their will? The researchers encouraged hypnotized people to perform a dangerous action (putting one hand in "acid" and throwing the "acid" into a reservoir). A day later, these hypnotized individuals entered the exhibit, with no knowledge of their behavior and categorically denied that they were following such orders. The hypnotized person appears to be listening only to the hypnotist's messages and responds in an uncritical, automatic manner, usually ignoring all aspects of the environment except those indicated by the hypnotist. In a state of hypnosis, a person tends to see, feel, smell, and otherwise perceive according to the suggestions of the hypnotist, even if these suggestions contradict the actual stimuli present in the environment. The effect of hypnosis is not limited to emotional changes. Most people do not remember what happened during deep hypnosis. This "posthypnotic amnesia" can result from spontaneous deep hypnosis or from the suggestion of the hypnotist while the subject is in a trance state. Amnesia can involve all events of the trance state or only selected ones, or it can appear in connection with matters unrelated to the trance.

Can hypnosis be therapeutic?

Hypotherapists try to help patients tap into their own healing powers (Baker, 1987). Posthypnotic suggestions have helped relieve headaches, asthma, and stress-related skin conditions. One woman, who had suffered from open sores all over her body for over 20 years, was asked to imagine her skin cleansed, glowing, swimming in sunlight and feeling smooth and flawless. Within three months, his wounds were gone (Bowers, 1984). A statistical analysis of 18 studies showed that, on average, 70 percent of clients improved when therapy was provided with hypnosis. Hypnosis has been particularly helpful in the treatment of obesity. However, drug, alcohol, and smoking addictions did not respond well to hypnosis.

Can Hypnosis Reduce Pain?

Yes, hypnosis can relieve pain. When people who are not sick put their hands in an ice bath, they feel intense pain within 25 seconds. If hypnotized people accept the command not to feel pain, they report that they actually feel little pain. Some dentists claim that even mild hypnosis can reduce fear and thereby reduce sensitivity to pain. The use of hypnosis in surgery has flourished in Europe, and one Belgian medical group has performed more than 5,000 operations using a combination of hypnosis, local anesthesia, and light sedation.

Conclusion: In conclusion, hypnosis blocks the state of consciousness, but not the state of unconsciousness. Hypnosis is used for a variety of purposes, as

detailed above. The role of hypnosis in human life is quite sufficient. Another person's mind can be manipulated based on the hypnotist's goals. It is advisable to use hypnosis only for positive purposes. Hypnosis is necessary for people because it relieves pain and helps to form a new worldview.

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